

“ To Evaluate polyherbal Extract for antioxidant activity”

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ABSTRACT

The antioxidant capacity of a herbal extract derived from two plants—*Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek) and *Phoenix dactylifera* (date palm)—was examined in this study. Several techniques were used in the laboratory to test the extract's capacity to reduce oxidation and neutralize dangerous free radicals. The results showed that the extract had strong antioxidant properties, similar to well-known antioxidants. It also contained high levels of phenolic compounds, which are believed to play a key role in these beneficial effects. Overall, the polyherbal extract from date palm and fenugreek has promising antioxidant potential and could be useful in health products like supplements or functional foods.

KEYWORDS: : *Phoenix dactylifera* (date palm), *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek), Antioxidant activity

INTRODUCTION

Numerous chronic diseases, such as diabetes, cancer, cardiovascular disease, and neurodegenerative diseases, are linked to oxidative stress, which is caused by an imbalance between the body's antioxidants and free radicals. Numerous compounds derived from plants are being investigated for their possible health benefits as a result of the growing interest in natural antioxidants as alternative therapeutic agents.

Two examples of plants that have long been utilized in a variety of therapeutic applications are *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek) and *Phoenix dactylifera* (date palm). Numerous bioactive substances, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and carotenoids, which are believed to have strong antioxidant qualities, are found in date palm, which is renowned for its abundant nutritional profile. Similar to this, fenugreek seeds have long been prized in herbal medicine for their many pharmacological properties, which are mainly ascribed to their saponins, alkaloids, and flavonoids. These benefits include anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.

Because of the synergistic interactions between their active ingredients, the combining of these two plants in polyherbal preparations may result in increased therapeutic effectiveness. According to recent research, extracts from *Trigonella foenum-graecum* and *Phoenix dactylifera* may have antioxidant properties because they may scavenge free radicals, prevent lipid peroxidation, and strengthen the body's natural antioxidant defenses. By examining their modes of action, phytochemical makeup, and the data demonstrating their ability to reduce oxidative stress, this study seeks to objectively assess the antioxidant potential of these two plant extracts both separately and in combination. The potential of these plant extracts may open the door to the creation of innovative plant-based methods for controlling or preventing illnesses linked to oxidative stress.

1. Introduction to Fenugreek (Trigonella-Foenum Graecum)

Trigonella-Foenum Graecum, or fenugreek, is regarded as one of the most promising and traditional therapeutic herbs. This plant's seeds and leaves are widely used in medicine as antioxidants, anti-diabetic, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer agents. Furthermore, it has been noted that fenugreek seeds have potent free radical scavenging properties.

Pharmacognostic Account of Fenugreek Seeds (Trigonella foenum-graecum)

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) is a popular herb belonging to the family Fabaceae, known for its medicinal, nutritional, and culinary uses.

FIG:Fenugreek leaf and seed

1. Chemical Composition:

Fenugreek seeds have a number of bioactive substances that give them their therapeutic qualities.

Trigonelline, a significant alkaloid, is one of the main alkaloids present in fenugreek seeds. It may affect the metabolism of glucose and has possible neuroprotective properties.

Flavonoids: The main flavonoids included in fenugreek seeds, apigenin and luteolin, are responsible for their antioxidant qualities. Trigonelline and other glycosides are known to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.

Trigonelline

Gentianine

2. Pharmacological Properties:

Hypoglycemic (Anti-Diabetic): Fenugreek seeds help in lowering blood sugar levels, making them useful in managing diabetes. The seeds contain soluble fiber, which may improve insulin sensitivity and reduce blood glucose levels.

Anti-Inflammatory: Due to the presence of saponins, flavonoids, and alkaloids, fenugreek seeds exhibit anti-inflammatory activity. They may help in conditions like arthritis and other inflammatory disorders.

Antioxidant: The flavonoids and other phenolic compounds in fenugreek seeds have antioxidant properties, which help combat oxidative stress in the body.

Date Palm Pharmacognostic Account:

Botanical Information

- Botanical Name: *Phoenix dactylifera* L.
- Family: Arecaceae (Palmae)
- Common Names: Date Palm, Date Tree,

Plant Description

- Evergreen tree, 15-30 m tall
- Leaves: Pinnate, 3-6 m long
- Flowers: Unisexual, in clusters
- Fruits: Drupes (dates), 2-7 cm long

Fruit Description

- Shape: Oval or cylindrical
- Size: 2-7 cm long, 1-3 cm wide
- Colour: Yellow, brown, or red
- Surface: Smooth, glossy
- Texture: Fleshy

Chemical structure:

Phenol

2,4-Dichlorophenol

(2-methylphenol) *o*-cresol

(3-methylphenol) *m*-cresol

(4-methylphenol) *p*-cresol

2,3,4,5,6- Pentachlorophenol

2,6-Dichlorophenol

4-chlorophenol

2,6-dimethoxyphenol

Catechol (2-hydroxyphenol)

4-Aminophenol (*p*-aminophenol)

4-Nitrophenol (*p*-Nitrophenol)

Chemical Constituents

- Sugars (27-45%): glucose, fructose, sucrose
- Fiber (8-12%): dietary fiber
- Minerals (2-5%): potassium, magnesium, iron
- Vitamins: A, C, E, K
- Phenolic compounds: flavonoids, phenolic acids
- Antioxidants: polyphenols

Pharmacological Actions:

- Hypoglycemic
- Hypolipidemic
- Anti-inflammatory
- Antimicrobial
- Antioxidant
- Hepatoprotective

Traditional Uses:

- Digestive issues
- Respiratory problems
- Skin and hair care
- Menstrual disorders
- Fertility enhancement

Pharmacological and Therapeutic Applications:

- Antidiabetic agents
- Cardiovascular health supplements
- Digestive enzymes
- Antimicrobial agents
- Skincare product

METHODS:

1. DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

With minor adjustments, the Alara et al. technique was used to assess the antioxidant activity of fenugreek seed oil. Briefly, 2 mL of DPPH (0.1 mM) solution was mixed with 0.2 mL of extract in methanol at different doses. After giving the mixture a good shake, it was allowed to sit at room temperature in a dark drawer for half an hour. The sample's absorbance was then determined using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi U-1800, Japan) set to 517 nm. As a blank, methanol was applied. In order to determine the scavenging activity on DPPH,

The half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of the sample was also calculated to find the inhibition percentage against oil concentration.

$$DPPH\ radical\ scavenging\ activity\ (\%) = \frac{A_{control} - A_{sample}}{A_{control}} \times 100$$

where A sample denotes the combination of sample (extracted oil) and DPPH solution, and Acontrol displays the absorbance of DPPH and methanol solution without sample.

Conclusion :

The polyherbal extracts of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek) and *Phoenix dactylifera* (date palm) may have shown notable antioxidant activity in this investigation. The extract's significant free radical scavenging activity was validated by the results of many in vitro tests (including DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP), which suggests that it may help shield cells from oxidative damage. The extract's antioxidant qualities are probably due to its high concentration of phenolic components.

The development of functional foods, dietary supplements, or other health products targeted at preventing oxidative stress and associated illnesses may benefit from this polyherbal extract's potential as a natural source of antioxidants. To investigate its possible therapeutic uses and long-term safety, more study is required.

REFERENCES:

1. Copley, M. S., Rose, P. J., Clapham, A., Edwards, D. N., Horton, M. C., & Evershed, R. P. (2001). Detection of palm fruit lipids in archaeological pottery from Qasr Ibrim, Egyptian Nubia. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London Series B: Biological Sciences.*, 268(1467), 593–597.
2. Sirisena, S., Ng, K., & Ajlouni, S. (2015). The emerging Australian date palm industry: Date fruit nutritional and bioactive compounds and valuable processing by-products. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety.*, 14(6), 813–823.
3. Zohary, D., Hopf, M., & Reeve, E. (1995). Domestication of plants in the Old World. *Genetical Research.*, 66(2), 181–182.
4. Khalid, S., Khalid, N., Khan, R. S., Ahmed, H., & Ahmad, A. (2017). A review on chemistry and pharmacology of Ajwa date fruit and pit. *Trends in food science & technology.*, 63, 60–69.
5. Zihad, S. N. K., Uddin, S. J., Sifat, N., Lovely, F., Rouf, R., Shilpi, J. A., et al. (2021). Antioxidant properties and phenolic profiling by UPLC-QTOF-MS of Ajwah, Safawy and Sukkari cultivars of date palm. *Biochemistry and biophysics reports.*, 25, 100909.
6. Sarraf, M., Jemni, M., Kahramanoğlu, I., Artés, F., Shahkoomahally, S., Namsi, A., et al. (2021). Commercial techniques for preserving date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) fruit quality and safety: A review. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences.*, 28(8), 4408.
7. FAO. Country Showcase, Dates 2020 [Available from: <http://www.fao.org/country-showcase/selected-product-detail/en/c/1287948/>. Accessed 28 Oct 2021.
8. Assirey, E. A. R. (2015). Nutritional composition of fruit of 10 date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) cultivars grown in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Taibah University for science.*, 9(1), 75–9.

9. Guido, F., Behija, S. E., Manel, I., Nesrine, Z., Ali, F., Mohamed, H., et al. (2011). Chemical and aroma volatile compositions of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) fruits at three maturation stages. *Food Chemistry*, 127(4), 1744–54.
10. Al-Harrasi, A., Rehman, N. U., Hussain, J., Khan, A. L., Al-Rawahi, A., Gilani, S. A., et al. (2014). Nutritional assessment and antioxidant analysis of 22 date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) vari-C
11. Al-Farsi M., Alasalvar C., Al-Abid M., Al-Shoaily K., Al-Amry M., Al-Rawahy F. Compositional and functional characteristics of dates, syrups, and their by-products. *Food Chem.* 2007;104:943–947.
12. X. Shi, T. Miyakawa, A. Nakamura, F. Hou, M. Hibi, J. Ogawa, Y. Kwon, M. Tanokura Engineering a short-chain dehydrogenase/reductase for the stereoselective production of (2S,3R,4S)-4-hydroxyisoleucine with three asymmetric centers
13. B. Annida, P.S.M. Prince Supplementation of fenugreek leaves reduces oxidative stress in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats
14. Ahmed, I.A., Ahmed, A.W.K. & Robinson, R.K. (1995). Chemical composition of date varieties as influenced by the stage of ripening. *Food Chemistry*, 54, 305–309